

Recommended citation: Courdier, M., & Schwaller, K. (2018). Has the engineering school trained you to innovate? Higher Apprenticeship Engineering Students' Progressive Innovation Skills Development. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 140-147). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672506.

**Has the engineering school trained you to innovate?
Higher apprenticeship students' progressive innovation skills development.**

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Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills

Keywords: Engineering skills, Innovation, Students' perception

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has progressively given a new definition to competitiveness. Due to their market expansion, companies have to cope with an increasing number of competitors. Innovation and opening up of the market to novelties are, thus, of utmost importance, and companies must cope with it. Innovation has also become a new standard for differentiation since it is the only process through which a company can propose something new. The (exact) same reasoning applies to engineering schools, since they are now open to foreign students and still consider visibility as a key element for a successful recruitment. Both students and professors now have the possibility to choose amongst all the schools in the world where they want to study or teach.

Top French engineering schools, 'grandes écoles', have trained the elite for the highest ranks in the society since the 17th century [1]. Until 1837, the engineers were former students of state schools: Military Engineering, Artillery, Arsenals, Mines Bridges and Roads were considered as the most successful innovators. However, even if engineer's skills are considered as the main investment to develop a successful innovation strategy [2], these high-end profiles often use their competencies in managerial positions and barely spend a few years with scientific-engineering occupation in technical fields. Using and taking innovation into account

for business purposes thus replaced the vision of innovation as a sole application of science with a new vision of innovation as a way to enhance competitiveness. This observation still stands today: “per capita, the number of start-ups launched in France is three times less than in the United States and for the number of patents registered with the World Intellectual Property Organization, two times less.” [3:p9]

In view of these observations, innovation in French engineering school becomes increasingly significant. As the very concept of innovation appears when technique is not taught as a reproduction of the world anymore but becomes a conception of the world [4], a technical thought emerges. The stake is now to train engineers able to link technique, business and innovation. Hence, apprenticeship students, benefitting from both academic technical inputs and business relationship with a real mission to carry on in their companies, need to be targeted. Over the past twenty years, lots of efforts have been made to improve apprenticeship training in engineering schools and, at the same time, the profession of engineer has evolved [5].

The objective of our study is to bring a better understanding of engineering apprentices' perception of their innovation skills. Therefore, we will try to answer the following questions:

- Do students consider they have been delivered an appropriate training to face the innovation challenges they will meet in their companies?
- What skills do they value as the most important for innovation purposes; and are they the best taught within their schools?
- To what extent does the otherness of the apprentices contribute to their training in innovation?

To answer these questions, we would like to explore the training of French higher engineering apprentice students, and particularly their innovation training program. A first part will deal with the bibliography study to help us understand the context. After that the methodology of study will be detailed, paving the way for the results. Eventually, the most interesting findings will be analyzed and compared to expectations and to the survey that was launched last year. The final section also showcases perspectives brought by this study, while still pointing the limitations out.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Increasing competition from different companies in the industrial sector pushes them to require their engineers to innovate, so as to stay constantly ahead of others. Thus, to prepare future engineers to be as effective as possible when they join the workforce, engineering schools need to adapt their teachings [6]: subjects that were not taught in such courses before now take an important place in the curriculum (communication, teamworking ability or intercultural thinking for instance). Thanks to those multidisciplinary teachings, students will be prepared for all kinds of situations they may encounter in their future careers. Passow [7] highlighted that these soft skills are perceived as the most important competencies – before science – by the graduate engineering students.

As innovation is a large subject and is exploited by many researchers, lots of definitions exist. Among those, we can note the Oslo Manual that is the most frequently used definition, which describes innovation as "the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations" [8:p46]. Innovation does not only involve the creation of innovative objects, such as smartphones or cars, but is also about social relations, marketing or communication. According to students, the interest is not to

be exclusively technical engineers but also to bring added value to the company. These multidisciplinary and ability to innovate enable students to climb easier on the hierarchical ladder, to obtain an ever-greater influence within the company and, above all, to gain an understanding of their ever-changing surrounding environment.

To companies, recruiting innovative engineers is crucial. According to Leiponen [9] (2005), “there are statistically significant complementarities between technical skills and innovation”. Indeed, Walton demonstrated in 2003 [10] that more than three quarters of managers regard creativity and innovation as vital for a company. These managers will thus choose innovative people to constitute their teams. Borrás and Edquist [11] (2015) also highlighted the fact that “organizations need to tap into external competencies in order to be able to reach its own innovation targets”. Freeman and Soete [12] (1997) went further, concluding: “not to innovate is to die”.

In this list of skills needed for innovation, Toner [13] observed that business, information technology and marketing are amongst the ones often observed in the innovating firms. There has already been some profound interest leading studies about the skills required for innovation; and even if our study does not aim at completing these, it is however important to emphasize that problem-solving abilities, multiple approach attitude, flexibility and responsibility, which have been identified as keys, are now always soft-skills.

Higher engineering schools are at the forefront of innovation trainings, due to the technical subjects they teach and due to the capacity they have to evolve and to propose more complete trainings, incorporating to incorporate soft skills. Nevertheless, they cannot be held solely responsible for the backwardness in innovation training [1]. Before joining engineering schools, most French students have attended preparatory classes that are in reality a two years high-level scientific course. On the one hand, these classes do give students true scientific capabilities but, on the other hand, they limit the time students spend working on projects, whether they are master’s thesis or innovative student’ contests [14]. At the same time, French engineers activities are not always technical. The Engineering Council (2010) [15] highlighted that approximately half of the British or German engineers are working in research or design, and only one third in France. If Munjal & Kundu (2017) [2] explained the historical reason, the fact remains that the training part dedicated to research activities in France is really smaller than in other countries. A good illustration of that phenomenon is that 15 % of US master’s students pursue their studies with a PhD, while only 4 % of the French do the same.

However, the apprentices may step apart from other students, as most of them did not receive the same previous background: a majority comes from technical degrees – which are in France much more practical – and thus has already worked on real projects for most of them. In this framework, apprentice engineer training should take advantage of the different levers offered by the otherness that its students developed. It would then fully benefit from the different capabilities of this student category. This can also benefit to “regular” students in mixed classes. [16]

2 APPLIED METHODOLOGY

Our research is based on both our literature review and our previous research study, and aims to complete the findings of last year study. Thus, our work is in the continuity of our previous study [17] and used the same sequential exploratory research design. In the framework of this first exploratory study, experimented engineers of various fields were interviewed to define which the most relevant innovation skills are. Then, those different skills were confronted to students’

perception through an online survey, aiming to determine whether or not students agree on this selection, and if they feel adequately trained to innovate.

A new online survey achieved the 2018 data collection. The same 2017 qualitative study results have been used to design this quantitative multiple-choice form in order to keep a similar sample of proposed answers. However, the survey differentiates the status of the respondents to focus on the apprentices. Some filter-questions have also been used to sort people out according to how long they did study in engineering school (first, second, or third year students) and how many years of experience (<1, 1-3, 3-5, >5) they do have. Such questions were also employed to sort out respondents according to the previous background they had before joining their respective schools (university, technical degree, or work in a company). Another difference with the previous study is that the survey has been widely broadcasted, enabling students of ten different engineering schools to express themselves. The common points between those ten engineering schools are:

- They have a higher engineering apprenticeship curricula,
- They do care about innovation as they met the opinion pollster at a student conference on this topic (pollster just presented the research at that time, and surveys have been sent online afterwards),
- Teachers accepted to forward the survey to their students.

The first set of questions aimed at knowing how apprentices engineering students perceive the 18 skills considered as important to innovate, while the second one helped us to draw up a list of their feedbacks regarding their trainings: do they think their school trained them well to innovate? Those two sets of questions were both needed to compare our answers with last years' results to underline that they are consistent. The need was also to check if there are still some contrasts, related to the sample disparity: apprentices sample vs students sample (students sample incorporate both apprentices (~20%) and "regular" (~80%) students).

Once we collected apprentices' opinion on their skills and their training, the last set of questions has been used to question them about how they would modify their courses to be better prepared to innovate. Let's remind that these students already have a professional mission, and that most of them are in contact with innovation within their companies. The propositions that have been incorporated in the form were those discussed and developed by a team of nine engineering apprentices of our school. They are a reflection of what those students already tried (e.g.: courses, project, entrepreneurial curriculum, business seminars) both at school and outside, and what they knew as already existing in others engineering or business schools.

The heterogeneity of our sample lies in the fact that questioned students are coming from various fields of study (e.g.: mechanics, electronics, biology, computer sciences, telecommunication, finance ...) or are specialized in different areas (as diverse as naval architecture, food science, or embedded systems for example), and in the ten schools sounded out. Respondents were asked to answer using a five-point Likert scale, so that analysis is rigorous and easy. We post-processed 144 different answers from 10 schools.

3 RESULTS

The results of our online survey show that students are aware of the importance of innovation in their future engineering profession. This is in accordance with the qualitative survey carried out by [Author1] (2017) [17], which indicated that confirmed engineers unanimously expressed the capital function of innovation to be a good contemporary engineer.

In order to understand how apprenticeship students perceive innovation, we asked the participants in our survey to assess the importance of 18 innovation skills on a 5-point Likert scale (0 being "not important" and 5 being "indispensable"). The results of this question clearly show that the most important skills for innovation are objective outlook (4.38/5), open-mindedness (4.33/5), and creativity (4.19/5).

We asked students to evaluate how their engineering schools prepare students for these same innovation skills. The comparison of the results for the two questions is illustrated in Figure 1.

Our results indicate that higher apprenticeship students consider that their engineering schools mainly prepare them to work as a team (3.86/5), multidisciplinary (3.75/5) and knowledge (3.71/5). These skills are indispensable in the technical engineering profession but are not vital to become innovative. It can be noticed that the three competencies cited previously as the most important in innovation are respectively valued at 3.01/5, 3.16/5 and 2.45/5. The difference between the required and real training level is the most important for these skills (Table 1). It has therefore to be noted that engineering schools are not focusing on the development of innovation skills but rather on the development of technical skills and knowledge, which will enable their student to become an efficient engineer on the technical level.

Fig. 1. "Level of importance vs. Level of integration" for innovation skills

Table 1. Marks and difference for each skill

Skill	Skill for innovation /5	Skill taught at school /5	Difference
Creativity	4.19	2.45	1.74
Open mindedness	4.33	3.16	1.17
Work experience	3.13	3.40	-0.27
Multidisciplinarity	3.53	3.75	-0.22
Technical expertise	3.29	3.54	-0.25
Relationship management	2.82	2.98	-0.16
Self-management	3.18	2.65	0.53
Ability to use ICT	3.41	3.71	-0.30

Critical thinking	4.08	3.11	0.97
Objective outlook	4.38	3.01	1.37
Leadership	2.75	2.40	0.35
Ability to work as a team member	3.75	3.86	-0.11
Communication	3.78	3.30	0.48
Analytical mindset	3.73	3.48	0.25
Knowledge	3.22	3.71	-0.49
Stress management	2.93	2.10	0.83
Problem-solving capacity	4.03	3.47	0.56
Project management	3.68	3.55	0.13

We then asked all participating students to evaluate their engineering schools' trainings according to how they prepare them for innovation. We split answers into three groups corresponding to the three years of the engineering apprenticeship cycle. Plus, we compared the results of the three school years in order to see if there was an evolution of the students' feelings towards their preparation for innovation. Results show that upon arrival in the first year of engineering school, students feel rather prepared to innovate (3.42/5). These are more students' expectations than a true feedback on training. On the contrary, at the end of the training cycle, in third year, students feel much less prepared for innovation (2.23/5) and highlight the fact that innovation is not a priority for engineering schools. Second-year students, in the midst of their training, evaluate this criterion at 3.01/5, which reveals a gradual declination as the training progresses. It is therefore possible to see that the engineering schools do not meet the innovation expectations of the various students integrating the three-years-course.

Finally, we asked the apprenticeship students if their academic or professional experience was the best way to develop innovation skills. Almost 60% of respondents answered that the combination of academic training and work experience is the ideal way to train for innovation. Interestingly, 38% of the students believe that professional experience is sufficient to develop this capacity, and only 2% believe that academic training is sufficient. The apprenticeship students show clearly, thanks to their experience, that the academic training only is not sufficient and that the curriculum they carry out, combining work and studies, is the ideal way to develop strong innovation skills.

The results we present in this paper should be discussed and compared to others, both from our previous study and from the literature. Thereby, apprentices' words about the needs of academic and professional experiences in their course are not a surprise. It has already been highlighted [18] that apprentices (who are shifting between a company and a school on a few weeks regular basis) improve their skills faster compared to "regular" students. This is especially right when it comes to responsibility and autonomy, two competencies that need to be mastered before being able to turn to innovation in an organization.

Also, what students feel, regarding their lack of preparation to innovate, was already known. Last year survey [17] clearly showed that 49.7% of the 2017 sample "do not feel sufficiently well-trained to innovate". What is more surprising, and this is the value of our study, can be found in the evolution of this feeling throughout the school curriculum. Indeed, we do not just confirm the previous results, but we also feature that engineering schools may fail in their duty since apprentices feel less prepared when leaving school. Before jumping to conclusion, let us remind that students still feel well prepared about their technical skills and that it confirms last year's finding about the quality of the engineering technical education. Thus, it could be said that the sensitivity of apprentices also evolves through their training on innovation topics,

and that students may gain awareness regarding a potential lack of competencies during their training.

4 CONCLUSION

To conclude, we can relate one more time that innovation skills are today needed for companies, in order to keep their position in the globalized markets. Companies are aware of this, and it seems that students also perceive that innovation skills are quite important in their training. However, this study shows that higher apprentices engineers perceive themselves as not (fully) ready to innovate. It looks like they hold their schools responsible for that, as they concentrate mainly on the development of technical knowledge and not sufficiently on the development of innovation skills and competencies. Moreover, students' expectations at the beginning of their training regarding courses and skills to be developed are not met, based on the feedback given by final year students.

A first comparison with last year study results highlights that there is no systematic discrepancy between hard and soft skills, and that students feel at ease in different competencies in those two domains, even if they also express a lack of confidence in other competencies. The balance takes place in other places, and the competencies for which a lack of training has been noticed are specifically the ones involving innovation; creativity ahead.

Our research also suggests that the best innovation training would be a mix between academic courses and professional experiences. Hence the apprenticeship appears to be the better formula to gain innovative skills, and even more when engineering schools seems unable to reach students expectations. The results of our survey suggest that the link between schools and companies should be reinforced to ensure a higher level on innovation capacity for higher-engineering students.

It should yet be noted that this study only concerns apprenticeship students from ten schools, and only partially reflects the reality of the whole country and of this type of training. However, this survey reveals the shortcomings in learning innovation in engineering schools.

To push the research further, we would like to add to last years and this year's comparative students' responses the view of their teachers, and particularly those implicated in the courses training. Are they aware of their students' feeling about their lack of preparation for innovation? Do they know that students would benefit from closer links to companies? Is there possible to improve higher engineering apprentices training? This study, combined with last year findings could give us a better understanding and a clearer view on how to develop engineering training, while always reducing the gap between reality and requirements.

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